

SUBSTITUTION IN THE BENZOPYRONE SERIES. PART III. SULPHONATION OF SOME 5-HYDROXYCOUMARIN DERIVATIVES

By J. R. MERCHANT AND R. C. SHAH

The sulphonation of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin, its methyl ester, their methyl ethers, 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, its methyl ether and 5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin has been described. The structures of the sulphonated products have been proved wherever possible.

The present work describes the results obtained by the sulphonation of some hydroxycoumarin derivatives with chlorosulphonic acid (vide this *issue*, p. 35).

In general, it has been observed that the 5-hydroxycoumarins are sulphonated more readily than the 7-hydroxy ones (Table I). As before, the sulphonic acids were identified by the analyses of their barium salts and by their derivatives with benzylisothiourea hydrochloride. The sulphonyl chlorides were characterised by the preparation of anilides.

5-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin (prepared according to Sethna *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228) with a moderate excess of chlorosulphonic acid at 100° furnished the 8-sulphonic acid (I) and a sulphonyl chloride (II). The yield of the latter was maximum when sulphonation was carried out in dry chloroform medium. Also, it could be easily hydrolysed by boiling with water into the free sulphonic acid. The dry sodium salt of this acid, when heated with an excess of chlorosulphonic acid, gave the same sulphonyl chloride as (II). The latter as well as its anilide are insoluble in sodium carbonate, indicating that the ester group in the original coumarin is not hydrolysed during sulphonation. However, this hydrolysis was easily effected by heating the sodium salt of the sulphonic acid with alkali on a water-bath, when 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonic acid was obtained. Attempts to prove the constitution of (I) by nitration or hydrolysis failed to provide definite products. The bromination of (I) was not carried out because the structures of the bromo derivatives of 5-hydroxycoumarins were not established at the time this work was carried out. The position of the sulphonic acid group in (I) was determined by the oxidation of its sodium salt with permanganate in alkaline medium, when a sulphonic acid of a phenol carboxylic acid was obtained. This indicates that the sulphonic acid group enters the 8-position in the coumarin. The analytical data of the oxidation product correspond to a dihydroxy-sulphobenzoic acid. It is found to be different from 2:4-dihydroxy-5-sulphobenzoic acid (cf. Part II, *loc. cit.*) and has therefore been assigned the structure 2:6-dihydroxy-3-sulphobenzoic acid.

The ester group in the original coumarin was hydrolysed when it was heated with a large excess of chlorosulphonic acid at 100°, affording the disulphonic acid (III) which was found to be identical with that obtained by the direct sulphonation of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin. When the latter coumarin, its methyl ester or the sulphonic acids (I) and (III) were heated at 140° with an excess of chlorosulphonic

acid, trisulphonic acids, (IV) and (VI), were obtained which from the analysis of the barium salts appeared to be that of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, decarboxylation and sulphonation occurring simultaneously.

Attempts to prepare a monosulphonic acid of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin by direct sulphonation were unsuccessful, even under mild experimental conditions. However, by heating it with 2.5 moles of chlorosulphonic acid, the disulphonic acid (III) was obtained. With 10 moles of chlorosulphonic acid under the same conditions, the monosulphonyl chloride (V) also separated out in addition to the disulphonic acid (III). Attempts to establish the structure of (III) by nitration afforded 5-hydroxy-3:6:8-trinitrocoumarin which was also obtained by nitration of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin and 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin under identical conditions. However, oxidation of its sodium salt with alkaline permanganate furnished 2:6-dihydroxy-3-sulphobenzoic acid, showing that the sulphonic acid groups in (III) had entered the 3:8-positions.

The structure of the monosulphonyl chloride (V) has been proved by hydrolysing it with water when a free sulphonic acid, identical with that obtained by hydrolysis of 5-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonic acid (I), is obtained. Sulphonation of 5-methoxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ester was incomplete at 30°-40°, whereas at temperatures between 50° and 60° it was accompanied with demethylation, the products obtained being the same as that obtained with the corresponding hydroxycoumarins.

No monosulphonated products were formed on sulphonation of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, but the disulphonic acid (VII) was easily obtained. Its structure was proved by its nitration in acetic acid medium when 5-hydroxy-6:8-dinitro-4-methylcoumarin was isolated, showing that the sulphonic acid groups in (VII) had entered the 6- and 8-positions. Attempts to prove the structure of the trisulphonic acid (VIII) failed to yield definite products. It was, however, assigned the structure 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin 3:6:8-trisulphonic acid from the usual rules of substitution.

5-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin on sulphonation in dry chloroform medium yielded a monosulphonic acid (IX). This acid did not give any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, indicating that no demethylation had occurred during sulphonation or if it had, the sulphonic acid group had entered the 3- or 8- position. Nitration of (IX) afforded a small amount of nitro compound free from sulphur (m. p. 140-45°). It could not, however, be sufficiently purified for purposes of analysis. No well-defined product could be obtained by the oxidation of (IX) with alkaline potassium permanganate. Hence, no definite structure could be assigned to (IX).

The sulphonation of 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin did not take place so readily as in the case of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin. When heated with an excess of chlorosulphonic acid at 100°, a monosulphonic acid (X) and a monosulphonyl chloride (XI) were obtained. The latter was also obtained by heating the sodium salt of (X) with an excess of chlorosulphonic acid. This gave a violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, showing that the sulphonic acid group in (X) had entered the 6-position. Nitration of (X) furnished a nitro compound, free from sulphur, which was assigned the structure 5-hydroxy-3:6:8-trinitro-4:7-dimethylcoumarin.

At 140°, with an excess of chlorosulphonic acid, 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin yielded a sulphonic acid, different from (X) in that it did not form any derivative with benzylisothiourea hydrochloride. It developed a violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and the analysis of its barium salt corresponded to a monosulphonic acid. The formation of the latter may probably be due to desulphonation of a higher sulphonic acid which might have been formed by sulphonation during concentration of the reaction mixture to obtain the barium salt.

From the sulphonation studies of 5-hydroxycoumarin derivatives, it appears that both the 6- and 8-positions are equally reactive. The sulphonation of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin furnishes only the 6:8-disulphonic acid, while that of 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin yields the 6-sulphonated products.

In the nitration of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, the first nitro group enters the 8-position. The nitration of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ester also lead first to the formation 8-nitro derivatives (Parekh and Shah, this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 335). On the other hand, the Fries migration of the acetate of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (Sethna *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, p. 232) and of 5-acetoxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin (Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1427) yields the 6-acetyl derivative in both cases.

Bromination of 5-hydroxy-4-methyl- and 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarins and their methyl ethers are found to yield first the 8-bromo derivatives in all cases (Lele, Parikh and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 610). The second bromine atom has been found to enter the 6-position in case of the 5-hydroxycoumarins and the 3-positions in the case of methoxycoumarins.

The 5-methoxycoumarins were easily demethylated on sulphonation, and hence, no definite idea could be obtained about the reactivity of the different positions.

Table I describes the different experimental conditions and products obtained on sulphonation of these coumarin derivatives.

TABLE I

Coumarin (C).	Moles of chloro-sulphonic acid.	Temp.	Heated for	Product of sulphonation.
5-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methyl-C	2.5	100°	2 hrs.	(I)-8-sulphonic acid (II)-8 sulphonyl chloride
	15	"	2	(III) 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-3:8-disulphonic acid.
	10	130°-140°	6	(IV) a trisulphonic acid
5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methyl-C	2.5	100°	2	(III)-3:8-disulphonic acid.
	10	"	2	(III)-3:8-disulphonic acid and (V) 8-sulphonyl chloride.
	10	140°	6	(VI) a trisulphonic acid.
5-Hydroxy-4-methyl-C	8	100°	2	(VII)-6:8-disulphonic acid.
	8	140°	6	(VIII)-3:6:8-trisulphonic acid.
5-Methoxy-4-methyl-C	1	60° (dry CHCl ₃)	1.5 "	(IX)-monosulphonic acid
5-Hydroxy-4:7-dimethyl-C	Excess	100°	2"	(X)-6-sulphonic acid and (XI)-6-sulphenyl chloride.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

All melting points are corrected. Freshly distilled chlorosulphonic acid was used. The products of sulphonation with their m.p. etc. are listed in Table II. The general method is the same as described in Part II (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II

Derivative of sulphonic acids and sulphonyl chloride

Sulpho- nation products.	M. P.	Barium salt/ Sulphonyl chloride	Barium Halogen.		S-Benzyliso- thiourea derivative Anilide.	M. P.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
I	—	$C_{24}H_{18}O_{16}S_2Ba$	17.3	18.0	$C_{20}H_{20}O_8N_2S_2$	222-24°	5.6	5.8
II	178-80°	$C_{17}H_9O_7ClS$	10.6	10.7	$C_{16}H_{12}O_7NS$	238-40°	3.3	3.6
III	—	$C_{11}H_6O_{11}S_2Ba$	26.1	26.7	$C_{27}H_{28}O_{11}N_4S_4$	209-10°	9.0	7.9
IV	—	$C_{10}H_{10}C_{21}S_2Br_{13}$	33.0	33.3	...	...	...	...
V	218-20°	$C_{11}H_7O_7ClS$	11.1	11.1	$C_{17}H_{15}O_7NS$	260°	3.4	3.7
			(C=41.9; H=2.7)			(decomp.)		
			(C=41.5; H=2.2)					
VI	—	$C_{20}H_{10}O_{24}S_6Ba_3$	33.3	33.3	...	...	...	...
VII	—	$C_{10}H_8O_9S_2Ba$	28.6	29.2	$C_{26}H_{28}O_7N_4S_4$	177-79°	8.1	8.4
VIII	—	$C_{20}H_{10}O_{21}S_6Ba_3$	33.0	33.3	...	...	...	...
IX	...	$C_{22}H_{18}O_{12}S_2Ba$	20.0	20.3	$C_{19}H_{20}O_8N_2S_2$	116-18°	6.0	6.4
X	...	$C_{22}H_{18}O_{12}S_2Ba$	19.2	20.3	$C_{19}H_{20}O_8N_2S_2$	182°	6.2	6.4
XI	164-66°	$C_{11}H_9O_5ClS$	12.4	12.3	$C_{17}H_{15}O_5NS$	201-203°	4.0	4.1

Hydrolysis of 5-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sodium sulphonate (I).—A solution of the substance (1 g.) in 10% NaOH solution (20 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath for 30 minutes, filtered and acidified, when a sodium salt separated. It was used for the preparation of the derivative with benzylisothiourea hydrochloride, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 198-200° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.3. $C_{19}H_{18}O_8N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.0%). The mixed m.p. of this derivative with that of the sulphonic acid obtained by hydrolysis of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonyl chloride (V) showed no lowering.

Oxidation of 5-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonic Acid (II).—To the sodium salt of the acid (3 g.), dissolved in 2N-KOH (40 c.c.), 4% solution of $KMnO_4$ (75 c.c.) was added dropwise, with ice cooling. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for 1 hour, filtered, and the filtrate concentrated and acidified, when a substance separated. It contained sulphur and it did not melt. A part of it was used for preparation of the barium salt, which was crystallised from water and dried at 140° for analysis. (Found: Ba, 22.4. $C_{14}H_{10}O_{14}S_2Ba$ requires Ba, 22.8%). The remaining part was used for preparation of the derivative with benzylisothiourea

hydrochloride. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 142-44°. It developed a violet coloration with EtOH-FeCl₃. (Found: N, 7.3. C₁₅H₁₀O₇N₂S₂ requires N, 7.0%). The same substance was obtained by the oxidation of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-3:8-disulphonic acid under identical conditions, and hence, it was assigned the structure 2:6-dihydroxy-3-sulphobenzoic acid.

Hydrolysis of 5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonyl Chloride (V).—The substance (0.5 g.) was boiled with water till a clear solution was obtained and then saturated with brine when sodium salt of the sulphonic acid precipitated. The S-benzylisothiuronium derivative was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 198-200°. The mixed m. p. with the derivative obtained from 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonic acid, described above, showed no lowering.

Nitration of 5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-3:8-disulphonic Acid.—The free disulphonic acid was obtained by decomposition of the barium salt. It crystallised from HCl (dil.) in white needles, m. p. 202-203°. The acid (0.6 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (16 c.c.) and nitric acid (d 1.42, 5 c.c.) was slowly added. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for 30 minutes and poured over ice when a yellow precipitate was obtained. It crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 208-209° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.2. C₁₀H₅O₉N₂ requires N, 13.5%). The same nitro compound was obtained by the nitration of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin and 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin under identical conditions.

Oxidation of 5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-3:8-disulphonic Acid.—The oxidation was carried out with alkaline permanganate, as described previously. The S-benzylisothiuronium derivative of the oxidation product had m. p. 142-44° and was found to be identical with that of 2:6-dihydroxy-3-sulphobenzoic acid, described before.

Preparation of 5-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—5-Methoxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin (3 g.) (prepared according to Sethua *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) was shaken with 10% NaOH solution (75 c.c.) and heated on the water-bath for 30 minutes to a clear solution. Acidification gave a white precipitate which crystallised in needles, m. p. 216-18°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.3. C₁₂H₁₀O₅ requires C, 61.5; H, 4.3%).

Nitration of 5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6:8-disulphonic Acid (VI).—The free sulphonic acid, obtained by decomposition of the barium salt (0.5 g.), was dissolved in acetic acid (5 c.c.) and nitric acid (d 1.42, 2.0 c.c.) was added dropwise with cooling. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and then poured over ice when a yellow precipitate was obtained which crystallised from methyl alcohol in yellow prisms, m. p. 182-84°. (Found: N, 10.2. C₁₀H₅O₇N₂ requires N, 10.5%). The mixed m. p. of the compound with 5-hydroxy-6:8-dinitro-4-methylcoumarin (prepared according to Parekh and Shah, *loc. cit.*, p. 338) showed no lowering.

Nitration of 5-Hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin-6-sulphonic Acid.—The free sulphonic acid was obtained as a precipitate during sulphonation of the coumarin on concentration of the filtrate after removal of the sulphonyl chloride. However, on trying to crystallise it, the sulphonic acid group was eliminated.

The crude sulphonic acid (0.5 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (8 c.c.) and nitric acid ($d = 1.42$, 4 c.c.) was added dropwise with cooling. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. On dilution with water, a yellow substance was obtained which crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m. p. $216-18^{\circ}$ (decomp.). It did not contain any sulphur. (Found: N, 12.6. $C_{11}H_7O_3N$, requires N, 12.9%). It was assigned the structure 5-hydroxy-3:6:8-trinitro-4:7-dimethylcoumarin.

INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE.
BOMBAY-I.

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